

Tracing N₂O from dairy processing sludge amended soil with visualizing microscale heterogeneity of NH₃ and pH (Short Communication)

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ABSTRACT

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from organic waste and animal slurry contribute to climate change and endanger our ecosystems. For the development of efficient mitigation technologies, in-depth knowledge of emission processes is needed. This can be obtained by non-destructive, temporal measurements of in-situ soil profiles and the transformation of ammonium (NH₄⁺) during events of emissions. Planar optode imaging is a non-destructive measuring method that can be used to visualize spatiotemporal changes of ammonia (NH₃) and pH in soil systems. In this study, soil amended with dairy processing sludge (DPS) was incubated in static chambers for 23 days, and GHG emissions, NH₃ concentrations and pH in the soil were measured simultaneously over time. The aim was to investigate the potential of applying different planar optodes to provide information that gives insight into processes of N₂O emissions. The DPS was applied to the soil as a surface layer (SL), with untreated soil as a control (CK). We were able to measure N₂O emissions while monitoring spatiotemporal changes of soil pH and NH₃ concentrations. The visualized microscale heterogeneity of the soil contributed to a better understanding of N₂O emission processes. While technical challenges (e.g., humidity sensitivity of the NH₃ optode and airtightness of the chambers) still need to be overcome, the method is a promising non-destructive method to study soil processes after application of different types of soil amendments.

1. Introduction

Recycling organic waste in agriculture replaces mineral fertilizers and contributes to a circular economy (Mayer et al., 2016). Dairy processing sludge (DPS) is clean and rich in phosphorus (P) and used as a P-fertilizer it contributes to the political goal of reducing P-import to Europe (Hu et al., 2021). However, land application of organic wastes is a source of greenhouse gases (GHG), such as nitrous oxide (N₂O) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). While the global warming potential (GWP) of N₂O is 273 times that of CO₂ (IPCC 2022), land application of organic wastes should be implemented with caution. The use of a non-destructive method for analyzing soil processes following the application of recycled organic fertilizers will contribute to broaden our understanding of emissions. This method can aid in testing and developing techniques to minimize emissions from recycled organic fertilizers, ultimately

enhancing the nutrient use efficiency of these new fertilizers. Furthermore, it will enable us to investigate their interaction with various soil types effectively (Shi et al., 2021).

N₂O emissions from soils are affected by chemical and biological processes, which are influenced by total ammonia nitrogen (TAN = NH₃-N + NH₄⁺-N), soil oxygen (O₂), pH, microbial activities, organic matter, etc. (Sommer et al., 2003), and these components vary in time and space. Planar optical sensors (i.e. optodes) for pH measurements have been applied to soil systems (Blossfeld et al., 2013), and recently an NH₃ optode was designed for NH₃ measurements at the air-soil interface and within the soil (Merl and Koren, 2020). Until now, there are few studies combining optodes with N₂O emissions and those studies only concentrated on soil O₂ and N₂O emissions (Zhu et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2017), which may not reveal a full map of the nitrification-denitrification processes occurring. Therefore, a novel

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planar optical sensor system that can continuously measure spatiotemporal concentrations of soil H^+ and NH_3/TAN are essential as it can contribute to enhance our knowledge about mechanism of N_2O production in and emission from soil amended organic waste.

In this study the objective was to examine the potential for providing a better understanding of N_2O production and emission from DPS applied to soil surface by using a combination of simultaneously measuring spatiotemporal changes of soil NH_3 and pH with optodes and N_2O emissions with static chambers.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Dairy processing sludge (DPS) and soil collection and characteristics

The DPS was obtained from a wastewater treatment plant of a dairy production factory at Videbæk, Denmark. It was stored at $-18\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until three days prior to the start of the experiment. The DPS dry matter (DM) of 18% of wet biomass and pH of 7.8, contained 6.9 % total N, 43 g kg^{-1} total P, 9.1 g kg^{-1} NH_4^+-N .

The soil used in this study was collected in February 2021 from an agricultural field belonging to Åstrup Gods located in Tølløse, Zealand, Denmark ($55^\circ 37' N$, $11^\circ 48'$). The soil was a sandy loam (clay 11.8 %, silt 12.3 %, fine sand 43.7 %, coarse sand 28.1 %, OM 4 %), with 37.6 % water holding capacity (WHC), pH of 7.7 (1:2.5 w/w soil/water ratio), contained 6.9 % total N, 0.31 mg kg^{-1} NH_4^+-N , 12.88 mg kg^{-1} NO_3^--N , 44.1 mg kg^{-1} Olsen-P, and 9.1 cmol kg^{-1} cation exchange capacity (CEC). After collection, the soil was passed through a 2-mm sieve and stored at $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and before the start of the experiment the soil was stored at room temperature ($20 \pm 1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for three days. The methods of characterizing properties of the DPS and soil are the same as described in Merl et al. (2023).

2.2. Experimental setup

In the experiment, each static transparent plastic chamber ($L \times W \times H$: $60 \times 41 \times 100\text{ mm}$) had a removable front wall and lid and was equipped with a semitransparent planar optical sensor (for NH_3 or pH) on an integrated glass window ($50 \times 50\text{ mm}$) at the front wall (Fig. S1), similar to that of Zhu et al. (2015). The imaging setup was prepared before the incubation and details of the optode fabrication, application, calibration, and data analysis of the NH_3 and pH optodes are described by Merl et al. (2023). The calibration curves are shown in Fig. S2. For each chamber, the soil was packed to reach the same soil bulk density (1.3 g cm^{-3}) and gravimetric water content (WC) (35 %), and 0.3 $\text{g fresh DPS per cm}^2$ was added to the soil covering the surface (SL) in an application equal to 20.7 $\text{mg NH}_4^+-N\text{ kg}^{-1}$ dry soil. The control treatment (CK) was maintained at the same WC as the SL treatment. Each treatment was made in triplicate for sampling and measurements of N_2O and CO_2 , and the NH_3 or pH optodes were applied to one of the triplicates.

2.3. Sampling, measurement, and data analysis

During the incubation (at $20 \pm 1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), the chambers were closed and imaged every 10 min for the first hour, and then the interval was changed to one image per hour (for 18 h), per 2 h (for 28 h), per 6 h (for 72 h), thereafter per 12 h until the end of the incubation. In another study, Merl and Koren (2020) found that NH_3 optodes are humidity-dependent, so the signals from the optodes are not providing a quantitative estimate but a qualitative measure showing the trends in NH_3 concentrations. At the end of incubation, the images of the optodes were converted into false color images representing NH_3 concentrations based on our calibration data as described by Merl and Koren (2020).

The gas collection for GHG measurements was conducted on days 0, 2, 5, 8, 11, 15, 18 and 23. On each occasion, two needles were injected through rubber stoppers into the headspace of each chamber as inlet and outlet (Fig. S3), and then 60 mL of ambient air was flushed with a

syringe through each headspace three times, after that chambers were closed again, and a 5-ml gas sample was taken from the headspace at time 0, 15, 30 and 45 min. The collected gas samples were transferred into 3-ml pre-evacuated glass vials (Labco Exetainer), and N_2O , CO_2 and CH_4 concentrations were analyzed by a Greenhouse Gas Analyzer (450-GC, Bruker, Germany). The analyzer was configured with two chromatographic channels – one channel included an electron capture detector (ECD) for N_2O analyses, and the other channel included thermal conductivity detector/flame ionization detector (TCD/FID) for CO_2 and CH_4 measurements. After measurements of gas samples from the GC, fluxes of GHG were calculated using the regression approach in the free-ware HMR in R (Pedersen et al., 2010). Treatment effects were tested using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test in the statistical software JMP® Pro 15 (JMP®, 1989–2023). All significant differences were accepted at the p-value (p) < 0.05 .

3. Results and discussion

During the incubation, the NH_3 concentration in the SL treatment measured at the soil-sludge surface (ROIs in Fig. 1a) was relatively high at the beginning and then decreased until 6 h after DPS application. Thereafter, the NH_3 concentration in SL increased again and reached a peak at day 2, whereafter it decreased and became non-detectable after 6 days. Results from the pH optodes in the SL treatment (Fig. 1c) showed an increase of pH from the surface of DPS at the beginning and after 2 days pH varied between 6.8 and 7.3 until day 9, thereafter it decreased to about pH 5 at the end of the incubation. In the CK, the pH was ~ 6.5 initially at the soil surface, and then increased to above 7, where it varied between 7.2 and 7.7 over time. It is seen that the transition zone of pH and NH_3 between layers appears to be sharp, which is caused by the small amount of liquid infiltrating the soil from the sludge that is having a high DM concentration, thereby limiting infiltration down into the soil.

The NH_3 increase may be related to an increase in pH in the surface layers, due to emission of more CO_2 than NH_3 (Hafner et al., 2017). For the SL, at the beginning of the DPS application, the water at the interface was not homogeneously distributed and there was a lower WC at the soil (35 % WC) than in the DPS (82 % WC), but with time the WC was balanced when water moved from the DPS to the soil. The water distribution might affect the optode-detected NH_3 signals due to the humidity-dependence of the NH_3 optodes. Because of a decreasing pH with time (Fig. 1c), most TAN in SL might have been in the form of NH_4^+ and could not be detected after day 6 (Merl et al., 2023). Small NH_3 concentration peaks in the CK were detected initially and after 2 days, probably due to nitrogen (N) mineralization when water was added to the soil.

There are discrepancies between pH values detected in-situ with pH optodes and those gathered with pH electrodes using the soil extraction method, where the optode-detected pH values were lower than the pH measured with a pH electrode. Differences between optical and potentiometric pH measurements but also between in-situ and soil extraction methods have been reported previously (Merl et al., 2023; Nielsen et al., 2017). The variances may partly come from the difference in the measuring principles of pH optodes and pH electrodes but also from different sample handling methods. The advantage of pH optodes is that they can be used to measure soil pH at different water contents whereas the use of pH electrodes usually requires a soil solution, which alters the soil properties.

The N_2O flux from SL was low until day 5, whereafter it increased and peaked on day 11, while the CO_2 flux trend was the opposite, with a higher flux before day 5 and a lower flux after day 11 (Fig. 2). The high initial CO_2 emissions resulted due to the DPS application (Hafner et al., 2013). With time, O_2 is reduced, thereby the nitrification rate decreased, and there is an increased potential for N_2O production during nitrification and denitrification (Khalil et al., 2004; Zhu et al., 2015). During the experiment, the standard error of the mean (SEM) for N_2O and CO_2

Fig. 1. (a) False color images from NH₃ and pH optodes at selected time during the incubation; (b) Temporal changes of NH₃(aq) concentration (ppm is mg L⁻¹) in top-layer soils at selected regions of interest (ROIs, labeled in numbers 1–3 in Fig. 1a); (c) Temporal changes of soil pH in top-layer soils at selected ROIs (labeled in numbers 4–6 in Fig. 1a) (NH₃ concentrations and pH are mean values of three positions; error bar indicates standard error of the mean (SEM)).

Fig. 2. (a) Fluxes of N₂O over time during the incubation; (b) Fluxes of CO₂ over time during the incubation (n = 3; error bar indicates SEM).

fluxes was relatively high, likely due to leakage of the used chambers. However, since the chamber leak could serve as a vent similar to field static chambers (Hutchinson and Mosier, 1981), its impact on gas fluxes is considered to be limited. The trends in emissions show how emissions of N₂O peak when TAN of the soil is transformed, and the decrease in the measured pH is an indicator of enhanced N₂O production potential.

The study shows, that combining different optodes together with measurements of N₂O emissions can contribute to a better understanding of how changes in pH and NH₃ affect the N₂O emissions. In the future, other optodes (e.g., for O₂ or CO₂) should be included.

4. Conclusion and outlook

The incubation of soil amended with DPS in optode-equipped static chambers, where N₂O and CO₂ emissions were measured while monitoring in-situ soil pH and NH₃ concentrations, shows that visualized heterogeneity of the soil microenvironment improves our understanding of N₂O emissions. However, in order to improve its applicability for prescreening different soil amendments before field studies, the optode measuring technology must be advanced by: a) establishing a humidity calibration of NH₃ optodes, b) developing methods to enhance the contact between soil phase and optodes, and c) improving the closed chamber method for gas measurements to better incorporate optodes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yihuai Hu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Theresa Merl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Johanna Pedersen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marie Louise Bornø:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Azeem Tariq:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Klaus Koren:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sven Gjedde Sommer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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